

HAUL ROAD DESIGN OPTIMISATION APPROACH FOLLOWING TECHNOLOGICAL CONSTRAINTS IN OPEN-PIT MINING

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ABSTRACT. Modern mining practices rely to a great extent on the application of numerical methods for establishing design alternatives, leading to significant economic benefits. In the current article mine haul road design and construction are treated as two interconnected problems – 1) selection of a suitable optimisation for haul road design and selection of an optimal pit design solution; 2) selection of a suitable technology for haul road construction. Based on previous research, the main factors which determine haul road design feasibility have been identified. They are used for the purpose of establishing the key performance parameters which define the optimality of a haul road design solution. An optimisation problem is defined, which relies on different design solutions and the alternatives for a feasible ultimate pit design. Solutions of this optimisation problem are expected to maximise the mine's long-term profit. Furthermore, statistical parameters were obtained providing insight into affirming why a certain design solution is more dominant to others in a more robust way.

Key words: haul road design, haul road construction, open-pit mining

Introduction

The design of an efficient haul road for an open-pit mine is one of the most essential elements of pit design problems. It is of utmost importance to optimise transportation costs, due to the high amount of costs in relation to the structure of total operational costs. Different authors point out that haulage operations can contribute from 49% up to 70% of the total operational costs (Mohutsiwa and Musingwini, 2015; Nancel-Penard et al., 2019). In addition, assuming different haul road design parameters can affect the ultimate shape of the pit, which can lead to the excavation of additional volumes of overburden and waste material or to cease the access to certain volumes of ore. Nonetheless, different approaches to haul road and pit design aim to maximise the overall revenue for the mining operation, utilising different numerical methods (Aleksandrova, 2007; Akay et al., 2013; Baek and Choi, 2017; Morales et al., 2017; Nancel-Penard et al., 2019; Yarmuch et al., 2020). As efficient as they could be, in many cases certain parameters (e.g. number of pit entry points, suitable road grade, etc.) may not be established in a solution from such algorithms. However, they can be used as guidelines for determining which design alternatives or solutions provided by a certain algorithm are feasible and therefore suitable for the establishment of the ultimate pit design with respect to technological constraints and operational safety requirements. Furthermore, the haul road design problem is treated as two separate problems, regarding ex-pit road design and ramp design (Yarmuch et al., 2020). Nonetheless, the results provided from each of the two solutions are related to one another and the overall optimality of each design alternative. In addition, both solutions should meet the constraints, deriving from the technological parameters, capabilities and size of the equipment. Therefore, the overall haul design problem can be divided into two interconnected problems – 1) selection of an appropriate optimisation approach for haul road design and selection of an optimal pit design solution; 2) selection of a suitable technology for haul road construction and maintenance. R. Thompson et al. (2019) have established an

interactive approach to the design phase and the operational phase of a haul road operation (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. The interconnectivity between structural, functional and maintenance design (Thompson et al., 2019)

Furthermore, the author has also established a trend line, based on previous observations, which shows that the utilisation of more formal design methods reduces significantly the possibility for accidents. Hence, in order to achieve a reliable and realistic solution for an optimisation problem, an overview of the capabilities and limitations of different optimisation approaches has to be made. This would require an overview of the technological constraints for road construction, as well as the haul road and pit design parameters which provide a guideline for optimisation algorithms and other design methods.

Haul road and pit design parameters overview

In terms of design parameters, in-pit and ex-pit haul road construction relies on the same principles: slope angle and bench height are dependent on the physical and mechanical properties of the rock types, road width directly corresponds to width of the truck model utilised and the work shift output of the pit (Zlatanov and Aleksandrova, 2005; Aleksandrova and Zlatanov, 2008; Aleksandrova, 2013; Koprev, 2015). Figure 2 represents the basic design of a trench and a “semi-trench” which corresponds to the geometry of an in-pit ramp design between the topography and a bench or between two sequential benches at an initial stage of mining (Koprev, 2016).

Fig. 2. Basic design of a trench (left) and “semi-trench” (right), depending on topography (Aleksandrova, 2013)

For each segment of a haul road the length of the road (L) can be calculated by the formula (Aleksandrova, 2013):

$$L = \frac{H}{i} \quad (1)$$

H – elevation passes or pit bench height, m;
 i – road slope grade, %.

A key requirement is that the road curvature must respect the turning radius of the utilised trucks. The road’s curvature radius (R) is calculated in the following manner (Thompson et al., 2019):

$$R = \frac{V^2}{127(U_{min} + e)} \quad (2)$$

where V – vehicle speed (km/h);
 e - super-elevation rate (m/m);
 U_{min} - coefficient of lateral friction supply.

Road width (W) as another crucial parameter can be calculated by either way (Baek and Choi, 2017; Koprev, 2017):

$$W = (1,5 \cdot L + 0,5) \cdot X \quad (3)$$

where L – number of lanes;
 X – width of haulage equipment, m.

$$W = n \cdot W + 2 \cdot y + x \cdot (n - 1) \quad (4)$$

where x – safety distance between the trucks carrybacks, m;
 y – distance between truck wheel and road end, m

$$(y = 0,5 \cdot x \text{ or } 0,5 + 0,005 \cdot V^2)$$

Earthworks regarding haul road construction involves (drilling and blasting), loading, hauling, unloading and bulldozing. However, in terms of ex-pit road design and construction, the problem is regarded mainly as an earthwork allocation problem, where the optimisation objective is to partition the optimised cut-to-fill-assignments in different earthwork sections with minimal movement between them (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Cut and fill road construction modelling with earth allocation optimisation problem (Ji and Borrmann, 2014)

Ramp design problems have a similar ultimate goal – rock mass allocation must be performed in the most cost-effective manner. However, in order for this to be achieved, the task is interpreted as a problem for obtaining an optimal ultimate pit design and a maximum sum of cash flows after obtaining a set of pushbacks leading to the ultimate pit. Hustrulid et al. (2013) point out that the main purpose of the ramp design is to provide access to the complex geometry of the ore body. It is also established that the location of the ramps can significantly change the overall slope angle of the pit and therefore influence the overall stripping ratio of the pit, as well as the profitability of the mining operation due to different volumes of rock mass (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Open-pit design parameters (Grenon et al., 2011)

In addition, the ultimate pit depth and topography can significantly influence the total length of the pit ramp segments, as well as the number of times the haul road spiral intersects a profile view of the pit’s slope (n). In such sections of the pit slope the overall slope angle is influenced by the number of intersections, which can be determined by the formula (Aleksandrova, 2013):

$$n = \frac{L}{0,5 \cdot (P_b + P_c)} = \frac{K \cdot H}{i \cdot (P_b + \pi \cdot h \cdot \cot g \alpha)} \quad (5)$$

where L – total in-pit haul road length, m;
 P_b – pit bottom contour length, m;
 P_c – pit surface contour length, m;
 K – haul road extension factor;
 H – pit depth, m;
 h – bench height, m;
 α – slope angle, °.

However, this formula works best for cases where only one rock type zone is present, and the ultimate pit shell can be approximated to a truncated cone. It has been stated that the actual value for n (as a real number) can be up to 15% higher than its true value, which from a practical standpoint provides a satisfactory level of accuracy. The overall slope angle can be calculated by applying the formula (Koprev et al., 2015):

$$\beta = \arctg \frac{m \cdot h}{W \cdot n + B \cdot (m - 1 - n) + m \cdot h \cdot \cotg \alpha} \quad (6)$$

where β – overall pit slope angle, °;
 B – berm width, m;
 m – number of benches;
 other symbols as described above.

To sum up, the main aspects, which must be considered for the design phase of the haul road include:

- **Maximum revenue for ultimate pit design.** Pit design should not cease access to valuable sections of the ore deposit and provide as much access to the ore body as possible. At the same time, the pit design should minimise waste volumes as much as possible in order to reduce unnecessary mining costs and the need for clearing more spaces for storing waste rock.

- **Minimum costs for the transport of rock mass throughout the life of mine.** Long-life haul roads are preferable than short-life roads as this reduces overall road construction costs and operating costs (Attkinson, 1992). Therefore, roads exiting from pit walls are more feasible. However, it should be kept in mind that this criterion is site specific due to the crusher location and the ore and waste dump locations (Hustrulid et al., 2013; Paricheh and Osanloo, 2016; Liu and Pourrahimian, 2020). Haulage costs are also related to the number of access points to the pit. More access points may provide greater flexibility, however, this may not be the best cost-effective solution (Hustrulid et al., 2013).

- **Maximum level of safety.** A crucial part of creating a safe work environment is the avoidance of areas or design parameters which can compromise the slope stability (Attkinson, 1992). In terms of operational safety, additional switchbacks may provide feasible solutions, however, it is established that switchbacks tend to slow traffic, cause greater tyre wear and various road maintenance problems (Hustrulid et al., 2013). Furthermore, sight distance is obligatory to be significantly higher than truck stopping distances, which requires a larger vertical radius both for in-pit and ex-pit haul roads.

- **Maximum productivity.** This is related to the road width which would minimise traffic congestion (Attkinson, 1992). This also corresponds to the required truck hours for the mining equipment, which can further minimise the fleet size and therefore minimise investment and operational costs. However, it should be kept in mind that excess road width may also improve slope stability, but it reduces the undiscounted profit of the mine.

- **Minimum level of ecological impact.** This aspect is related to maintaining a low artificial footprint on the surrounding areas in terms of noise levels, dust generation, CO₂ emissions, as well as the possibility of waste rock utilisation for bed materials.

All the aforementioned factors are related to the key design parameters of the haul road design both for ex-pit and in-pit conditions. At the same time, both cases of in-pit and ex-pit road constructions aim at minimising haul distances, due to its direct impact on the operational costs during the life of mine. Hence, different approaches regarding this optimisation problem have been established which target complementing minimal investment costs with minimal operational costs whenever possible.

Existing algorithms and approaches

Even though the construction of ex-pit haul roads and in-pit ramps have a similar technological process, earthworks sequencing and optimal design parameters estimation, the design process regarding optimisation techniques and suitable approaches can vary significantly. The reason for this separation of different approaches is that each optimisation problem focuses on a specific set of parameters which can be calculated by repeating operations representing different scenarios.

Ex-pit haul road design algorithms

This part of the optimisation problem is related to other civil engineering problems such as the construction of roads belonging to the state road network, roads serving the forest industry as the construction of these types of roads require lower stripping activities, compared to the mining industry. Therefore, certain approaches have already been established which provide practical solutions.

Road Layout simplification algorithms

The application of line simplification algorithms is performed to minimise transport distances via eliminating vertices for achieving an appropriate road design. Apart from applying a conventional Euclidean Distance method a number of times for the road layout, line simplification algorithms can also be applied, which include the following algorithms: Wall-Danielson (Wall and Danielson, 1984), Latecki-Lakamper (Latecki-Lakamper, 1999), Douglas-Peucker (Douglas and Peucker, 1973), Visvalingam-Whyatt (Visvalingam and Whyatt, 1993) and the Zhao-Saalfeld algorithm (Zhao and Saalfeld, 1997). Out of the listed above, the Douglas-Peucker algorithm has been successfully used in a haul road optimisation problem for open-pit mines as a complementary approach to the design problem (Baek and Choi, 2017). Mondal et al. (2015) develops a bi-level programming model for the optimisation of the horizontal alignment in a specified corridor as well as a globally optimal vertical alignment. Casal et al. (2017) have presented a method for the optimisation of horizontal alignment roads (which are composed of circular curves and tangent line segments joined by means of transition curves). As simple as it may be, this approach provides a basis for minimising operational costs due to the minimisation of haul distances.

Discrete optimisation techniques

On the other hand, discrete optimisation techniques have been widely used to design roads in forest operations. One of the most applicable approaches consists in dividing the terrain into cells and then associating with each cell a certain set of nodes to represent the directions in which the cell can be accessed.

Digital elevation models allow the discretisation of the terrain in cells with a cubic shape or with different sizes for their three dimensions. In addition, unlike geological block models, cells in earth allocation problems could have smaller sizes without the concern of decreasing the accuracy of estimations, as ex-pit road cell databases do not need to have attributes regarding ore grades or other geochemical contents. However, a smaller cell size and a higher number of neighbours would increase the resolution of the model, but

makes it harder to solve (Heinimann et al., 2003; Stükelberger, 2008).

The raster-based least cost path analysis (LCPA) method has mainly been used to analyse and determine the optimum path at the local scale such as paths for a pipeline, material transportation at a construction site and last but not least mining haul road design (Baek and Choi, 2017). The LCPA method consists of two steps: 1) the cost of passing every cell from the origin is calculated based on the cost surface data, which contains the cost of passing each cell, and these values are recorded in every cell and 2) the least-cost path is derived using the back-link mechanism based on the calculation results of the accumulated travel cost recorded in all cells.

In-pit ramp design methods

Block model approach

The block modelling approach is one of the most powerful and successfully implemented methods for solving mining problems, regarding the optimisation of the pit contour, establishing pushbacks and scheduling mining operations, whenever a vast number of technologically feasible solutions exist. The principles of applying directed graphs are similar to the ones implemented in ex-pit haul road optimisation algorithms. Figure 5 represents the set of blocks which are responsible for maintaining the technological feasibility of the ultimate pit contour by removing blocks, which are standing in potential ramps locations.

Fig. 5. Ramp set, blocks b and b' selected as accesses: green blocks are in the path, yellow blocks have to be removed due to precedence constraints; (left) Resulting profile after ramp construction (right) (Nancel-Penard et al., 2019)

Depending on the position of the two blocks the slope and width of the ramp can be adjusted for obtaining the potential ramp location candidates. The objective function of this algorithm is to maximise the economic value of the removed blocks from the block model (including the blocks representing the ramp entry and exit points). The nodes of each cell are then connected to the nodes in the neighbourhood cells, creating a graph that represents possible paths. Thus, grade constraints, as well as constraints regarding the turning radius of the ramp can be incorporated into the problem.

This approach has several modifications of the algorithm used for obtaining an optimal solution in the search space of the directed graph, as more notable solutions are provided by Morales et al. (2017), Nancel-Penard et al. (2019), Yarmuch et al. (2020), etc.

Limitations of existing algorithms and methods

Ex-pit haul road algorithms

Existing ex-pit haul road algorithms have some limitations regarding the identification of a best road solution – some authors formulate the objective function to solve the earthworks allocation problem (which corresponds to minimising investment costs for road construction), while others focus on the objective to minimise the complexity of the polyline to achieve a smaller travel distance (which serves as a tool for minimising operational costs). Raster-based approaches and LCPA algorithms provide a good basis for practical and future design work, which solve both problems. However, as a directed graph problem, they face the problems all similar problems have – when the complexity of the graph is increased, heuristic methods are required to be utilised in order to obtain a solution, in terms of a practical time constraint. Another alternative is to simplify the problem and neglect certain parameters which may lead to conflicting solutions, when ultimately all design parameters are considered by the designer. Undoubtedly, the solutions from the different types of computer-based approaches can be time-saving, to some extent they remain suboptimal, considering the vast number of factors required for simultaneous optimisation. As in every optimisation problem, in rare cases not every constraint can be met, thus some constraints have to be relaxed, which leads to relying on the parameters in the objective function. Nonetheless, they are irreplaceable tools to engineers and are further developed to exceed their current limitations.

In-pit ramp methods

In-pit methods have similar problems to the ones mentioned for ex-pit haul road algorithms. Although in-pit design algorithms based on block models can produce an optimal solution from a wide range of calculated pit models, the main limitation of such approaches is the inaccuracies of the calculated result from the block model to the actual geometry of pit design. Adjustment of block sizes of a block model in order to meet the adequate size suitable for ramp geometry parameters (width, length, slope) require tampering with the block model ore grades for each sub-block inside a parent-block which may lead to minor but nonetheless false interpretations of the spatial distribution of ore grade and other attributes from the geospatial model. And last but not least, approaches based on directed graph representations of the ultimate pit problem rarely establish an early estimation of haulage costs (other than the presupposed haulage costs in the sum of mining costs), deriving from ramp lengths besides the total profit value of the ultimate pit. Therefore, most authors focus mainly on optimising the total profit of different ultimate pit scenarios and neglect the true nature of operational costs. Truly, they can be calculated in a more robust way during pushback definitions and scheduling.

Scope of study

As it has already been pointed in the overview made, different optimisation problems inevitably disregard certain parameters, which are further calculated for the post-optimisation solutions during the design process and the determination of an optimal pushback sequence. In cases where solutions from optimisation algorithms are well segregated such an approach is truly accurate, as the assumed inaccuracies are irrelevant. Based on a brief

overview of the existing optimisation approaches, the current paper's main focus is on the in-pit ramp design problem as a potential starting point for minimising the search space for the optimisation algorithms. In addition, this approach could provide an interpretation of a potential threshold value which the absolute difference between the optimised parameters (in-pit haul distance, total profit, stripping ratio, etc.) of the design solutions from optimisation algorithms should exceed, in order for them to be ranked in a more reliable way. Therefore, cases which have subtle differences between the key performance parameters have to be further investigated and ranked when reducing them to a detailed ultimate pit design.

Case study

Aim of the study

This paper aims to propose an optimisation approach, which utilises an already established result from a certain block model optimisation solution for the development of a realistic open-pit design surface. The proposed steps could be repeated a number of times, depending on the desired number of candidates for a specific design alternative and the desired level of confidence one wants to achieve. The result from these actions allows the user to make an initial assessment of the feasibility of each ultimate design result in a more robust way by including an approximate preliminary calculation of haulage costs before introducing pushbacks. Afterwards, each ultimate design is compared to all other results, which leads to the establishment of the most feasible design or to the point where certain optimisation parameters need to be relaxed and more ultimate pit designs need to be investigated.

Preliminary information

Automated pit design provides the instantaneous creation of technologically feasible pit designs after the optimisation process has been completed by a certain algorithm. This approach complements block model approaches and serves as a basis for further pit design adjustments to be generated in each pit for the sequence of mining operations. This approach may be more time consuming than heuristic approaches based on algorithms solving directed graphs as it requires some manual work, but it provides a more accurate way for obtaining volume calculations and design solutions which fully respect the technological constraints of an open pit mine, e.g. the curvature radius, the superelevation of the in-pit haul road, the need of horizontal sections between ramps on consecutive benches, etc.

A case study is presented here treating the haul road optimisation problem as part of the ultimate pit design optimisation problem. The current gold deposit, used for this case study is suitable for mining and extraction for a period of 35 years with an annual ore output of 500000 t/a. The whole procedure of obtaining a "fine-tuned" ultimate pit design is presented in Figure 6.

Initially by using the block model of the deposit an economical model was obtained using a standard methodology of including mining costs for ore and waste material as well as processing costs for the ore. The exact values for these costs cannot be provided due to commercial confidentiality. However, an approximate value for mining costs can be provided which was estimated to be approximately 48 \$/t regarding ore.

Fig. 6. Assumed procedure for obtaining a "fine-tuned" ultimate pit design

This includes mining costs, waste rock costs, processing costs, administrative costs, royalties and selling costs. The assumed price of Au was 58 \$/g. Furthermore, for confidentiality reasons the obtainable profit for the ultimate pit design candidate used in this paper are provided as standardised values depending on the maximum profit value out of all the considered alternatives.

Apart from the overlaying clays above the ore zones, for the most part rock types for the deposit remain consistent with an average density of approximately 2.7 t/m³ for siltstones with a high density of quartz inclusions. These conditions are suitable for establishing a bench height of 15 m for the ultimate pit design with a slope angle for each bench of 60°. The bench width was assumed to be 6 m.

Following the well-established approach of obtaining a solution of the extent of the open-pit mine, the Lerchs-Grossman optimisation algorithm was utilised for the economic model, providing an ultimate pit shell. For the sake of establishing a technologically feasible pit contour the overall slope angle was utilised as a constraint for the algorithm. However, in order to achieve a more realistic pit contour depending on the pre-supposed ramp grade and the number of intersections per profile line, an ultimate pit shell was generated, by utilising an overall pit slope angle of 42°. By applying formulae (5) and (6) the following results were established:

$$n = \frac{L}{0,5 \cdot (P_b + P_c)} = \frac{1800}{0,5 \cdot (677 + 1693)} = 1,5 \quad (7)$$

$$n = \frac{L}{0,5 \cdot (P_b + P_c)} = \frac{2150}{0,5 \cdot (677 + 1693)} = 1,8 \quad (8)$$

Two intersections were assumed for the following formula:

$$\beta = \arctg \frac{10.15}{20.2 + 6.7 + 10.15 \cdot \cot g 60^\circ} \approx 42^\circ \quad (9)$$

After obtaining a pit shell from the Lerch-Grossman algorithm, three alternative approaches can be undertaken for establishing the candidate locations for ramp locations and design parameters depending on the design direction: 1) pit bottom – pit contour (up); 2) pit contour – pit bottom (down) or 3) combined approach. Each of the three approaches is valid. For the sake of simplicity, the first approach was utilised in this case study due to the shape of the ore body, which is more suitable for the pit bottom – pit contour approach. Hence, a small volume of ore could remain unextracted with this approach at the lower benches of the pit, compared to the other two alternatives.

Following the steps of Nancel-Penard et al. (2017) and D. Liu et al. (2020), initially 4 candidate points were considered for the pit bottom string for each of the two assumed cases of road grade (8% and 10%), which lead to the consideration of more candidate points during the process. Figure 7 represents the pit bottom string, the 4 initial candidate points and the 4 secondary candidate points for the second iteration. Afterwards, each scenario provides an end-point for the uppermost ramp, intersecting the topographic surface and the pit contour. A manual approach was utilised to connect the pit's entrance point to the state road network as well as the same entry point to the waste dump location.

Fig. 7. Candidates for ramp starting point located on a search space of the pit bottom string

Road width was calculated to be approximately 20 m, while the turning radius was assumed to be 25 m for a maximum speed of 20 km/h and superelevation of 3%. Coefficient of lateral friction was assumed to be 0.16 (Koprev et al., 2017). The key performance parameters were considered for the choice of a dominant design solution. Initially the considered parameters for this analysis included:

- 1) **volume of minable ore** – volume of ore with grade higher than the cut-off grade, which remains inside the ultimate pit surface;
- 2) **volume of minable waste** - volume of waste which is to be mined for establishing the shape of the ultimate pit surface;
- 3) **stripping ratio** – stripping ratio value for the pit surface with a value lower than the maximum allowable stripping ratio;
- 4) **total undiscounted profit** – overall financial results of the mining operation, calculated by the designed ultimate pit model and according to the pushback direction;
- 5) **total area of the pit contour** – this area can be interpreted as the disturbed area for reclamation, after the end of LOM (life of mine);
- 6) **total amount of CO₂ truck emissions** – ecological footprint of the mining operation;

7) **total amount of truck hours** – parameter used for determination of total fleet size, which indirectly corresponds to operational safety.

However, several of the aforementioned parameters are collinear as some of them are extended variants of the other. Therefore, in terms of feasibility of the mining operation the parameter **total undiscounted profit** is used for ranking all design alternatives. The ecological impact of the mining operation is described with the **total amount of CO₂ truck emissions**. The total amount of truck hours is collinear with the amount of CO₂ emissions and therefore is neglected as a key parameter. The total area of pit contours differs up to 10 decares which is not negligible, however the total pit area was used as a complementary parameter.

To establish a better understanding of the feasibility of each design alternative, apart from the general approach of calculating the undiscounted profit for the ultimate pit based on the block model, an approach similar to the one of Yarmuch et al. (2020) has been utilised. The total amount of ore and waste volume which is situated on each bench is assumed to be transported from the pit through the ultimate ramp design configuration. It is well-known that that ramps and in-pit haul roads are not constantly available or existing during the life of mine, which inevitable would complicate the problem. Nonetheless, two principal pushback scenarios exist, which provide an insight into other more realistic scenarios (Figure 8). The picture on the right represents a conventional pushback scenario, while the one on the left shows the bench-by-bench pushback scenario, which is not a realistic one. However, it has been established in previous research by other authors as an approach for a similar problem (Anachkov and Konstantinov, 1985).

Fig. 8. Pushback configurations for open-pit mining. Bench-by-bench (left). Realistic pushbacks (right)

Nonetheless, in terms of haul distances it needs to be further investigated whether this approach provides a pessimistic or optimistic estimation of operational costs. For the current case study, it was assumed that the bench-by-bench pushback approach is in action and the volume for each bench is hauled from its respective depth.

After ranking all design alternatives on the calculations made only for the initial 4 candidate points for the start of ramp, the secondary 4 candidates were included in the analysis. This applies for both scenarios of the haul road slope grade. This step is conducted in order to limit the search space and look for other potential solutions. This approach can be done any number of times, but for the sake of simplicity it has been done only twice for this case study.

Last but not least, all design alternatives from the considered scenarios are ranked according to their total undiscounted profit and total amount of CO₂ truck emissions.

Results

Two scenarios have been considered (clockwise and counterclockwise ramp directions) for two design alternatives (8% and 10% ramp grade). The same starting points for the locations of the candidate ramp designs were used for both scenarios and slope grade. Table 1 shows the results for the clockwise scenario.

Table 1. Scenarios for 10% grade of ramps

Candidate	Scenario	Ore Volume [Mt]	Waste Volume, [Mt]	Stripping Ratio	In-pit Haul Distance [m]
1	CW	17.07	19.94	1.17	1862.6
2	CW	17.02	19.58	1.15	1812.2
3	CW	16.98	19.76	1.16	1761.8
4	CW	16.91	19.89	1.18	1741.6
5	CW	16.88	19.68	1.17	1638.7
6	CW	16.96	19.76	1.17	1614.9
7	CW	16.96	19.93	1.18	2069.5
8	CW	16.96	20.52	1.21	1869.3
1	CCW	17.05	19.64	1.15	1753.4
2	CCW	16.96	20.21	1.19	1855.7
3	CCW	16.96	20.12	1.19	1943.1
4	CCW	16.97	19.86	1.17	2026.8
5	CCW	16.99	19.91	1.17	1862.6
6	CCW	16.91	19.95	1.18	1732.0
7	CCW	16.91	19.66	1.16	1590.8
8	CCW	16.99	19.26	1.13	1639.4

* CW – clockwise, CCW – counterclockwise

Table 2. Scenarios for 8% grade of ramps

Candidate	Scenario	Ore Volume [Mt]	Waste Volume, [Mt]	Stripping Ratio	In-pit Haul Distance [m]
1	CW	17.08	21.37	1.25	2035.3
2	CW	17.07	21.21	1.24	1939.5
3	CW	17.03	21.52	1.26	2010.7
4	CW	16.98	21.75	1.28	2121.7
5	CW	16.96	21.85	1.29	2246.6
6	CW	16.99	21.92	1.29	2421.1
7	CW	16.98	21.72	1.28	2464.7
8	CW	16.97	21.90	1.29	2220.0
1	CCW	17.07	21.43	1.26	2057.6
2	CCW	16.98	21.78	1.28	1966.9
3	CCW	16.98	21.65	1.27	1912.5
4	CCW	16.99	21.42	1.26	2507.1
5	CCW	17.01	21.69	1.28	2399.1
6	CCW	16.98	22.10	1.30	2209.1
7	CCW	16.99	21.55	1.27	2199.4
8	CCW	17.06	21.19	1.24	2112.2

* CW – clockwise, CCW – counterclockwise

As it can be observed, different locations of the candidate points can lead to a change of the overall pit shape, as well as the in-pit haul distance. Therefore, in order to evaluate properly each design alternative, haul costs must be recalculated for

each designed pit with respect to the established in-pit haul distance.

The hourly fuel consumption (FC) (L/h) was established using Hays (1990) model by applying the formula:

$$FC = (CSF \cdot P \cdot LF) / FD \quad (10)$$

where CSF - the engine-specific fuel consumption at full power (0.213 – 0.268 kg/kWh);

P - power (kW),

LF - engine load factor;

FD - the fuel density (0.85kg/l for diesel).

Values of engine load factor are given by Kecojevic and Komljenovic (2010), as follows:

- Low: 20%-30% (Continuous operation at an average gross weight less than the recommended. Excellent haul roads. No overloading, low load factor.)

- Medium: 30%-40% (Continuous operation at an average gross weight approaching the recommended. Minimal overloading. Good haul roads, moderate load factor.)

- High: 40%-50% (Continuous operation at or above maximum recommended gross weight. Overloading. Poor haul roads, high load factor.)

Figures 9-12 show that optimality of a candidate pit can change with the methodology utilised for calculation of the undiscounted profit. The in-pit haul distance result neglects ex-pit roads and therefore overestimates the calculated value for the undiscounted profit. In contrast, the in-pit and ex-pit haul distance result in a more realistic estimation of the undiscounted profit with respect to haul distances and ore and waste volumes inside the pit contour.

Fig. 9. Undiscounted profit for different optimisation approaches. Clockwise case. Grade: 10%

Fig. 10. Undiscounted profit for different optimisation approaches. Clockwise case. Grade: 8%

Fig. 11. Undiscounted profit for different optimisation approaches. Counterclockwise case. Grade: 10%

Fig. 12. Undiscounted profit for different optimisation approaches. Counterclockwise case. Grade: 8%

In addition, in this case study the in-pit haul distance result correlates highly with the combined haul distance result ($R^2=0.8269$ for the 10% road grade and $R^2=0.892$ for the 8% road grade design alternative). This can be attributed to the shorter ex-pit haul distances compared to the in-pit roads, which leads to a higher level of significance for the in-pit haul road design alternatives in terms of the ultimate pit design.

Although, certain values for the estimated profit of the post-optimisation designed pit result are very close to the combined haul distance approach, a low level of correlation is observed between the two data sets. Therefore, the undiscounted profit, calculated by the in-pit and ex-pit combined haul distance is assumed to be the more accurate performance parameter, following an approach similar to the one established by Yarmuch et al. (2020):

$$\text{Total undiscounted profit} = \text{Pit profit}' - \sum_{i=1}^m V_i \cdot L_i \cdot c \quad (11)$$

where *Pit profit'* – pit profit with reduced haulage costs, \$;
 V_i – total volume of ore and waste on bench i , t;
 L_i – in-pit haul distance for each bench to the topography surface, m;
 c – haulage costs, \$/t;

In addition, the total amount of CO₂ emissions was attempted to be calculated for each of the designed pits using field data acquired by Keccojevic et al. (2010). The CO₂ emission from diesel fuels in t/h can be calculated by the following equation:

$$CO_2 = FC \cdot CF \quad (12)$$

where FC - diesel fuel consumption (L/h),
 CF - the conversion factor.

The conversion factors of CO₂ emission for diesel fuel are calculated using the following dependencies (Keccojevic et al., 2010):

$$CF = CC \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 0,99 \cdot (44/12) \quad (13)$$

where CC - carbon content for the diesel fuel (g/L)
 0.99 - the oxidation factor.

Data, provided by Keccojevic et al. (2010) was used to calculate the CO₂ emissions for the CAT 772 truck model. It was assumed that fully loaded trucks have high engine load for 10% ramps, medium load for 8% ramps and low load for empty trucks moving downslope. Values for the total amount of CO₂ emissions were standardised using the following equation:

$$X_{st} = \frac{X_{min}}{X_i} \quad (14)$$

A similar approach was used for standardising the values for the undiscounted profit:

$$Y_{st} = \frac{Y_i}{Y_{max}} \quad (15)$$

As key performance parameters, CO₂ emissions are required to be minimised, while the undiscounted profit should be maximised. Therefore, all standardised variables have a maximum value of 1, which is considered to denote each design alternative which is the most optimal regarding both parameters. The values for the key performance parameters are represented for the Clockwise scenario shown in Table 3. Results from both scenarios and design alternatives regarding candidate points have been presented on Figures 13-14.

Fig. 13. Solution optimality coherence for Clockwise scenario with a ramp grade of 10%

Fig. 14. Solution optimality coherence for Clockwise scenario with a ramp grade of 8%

For a design to be optimal, if possible, both curves have to reach a value of 1 simultaneously.

Table 3. Clockwise scenario standardised performance parameters (grade: 10%)

Candidate	Scenario	Area [dka]	Standardised CO ₂ emissions	Standardised undiscounted profit
1	CW	173.1	0.7800	0.9820
2	CW	174.5	0.8324	0.9844
3	CW	177.0	0.8478	0.9834
4	CW	179.1	0.8439	0.9786
5	CW	178.1	0.9161	0.9825
6	CW	173.4	0.9614	0.9910
7	CW	170.9	0.6750	0.9615
8	CW	173.5	0.7646	0.9731
1	CCW	175.0	0.7730	0.9796
2	CCW	176.4	0.7609	0.9729
3	CCW	174.8	0.7335	0.9697
4	CCW	172.5	0.7065	0.9665
5	CCW	170.9	0.7833	0.9775
6	CCW	177.7	0.8049	0.9744
7	CCW	179.2	0.8535	0.9796
8	CCW	174.6	1.0000	1.0000

Results regarding the counterclockwise scenario are shown in Figures 15 and 16, as well as on Table 4.

Fig. 15. Solution optimality coherence for Counterclockwise scenario with a ramp grade of 10%

Fig. 16. Solution optimality coherence for Counterclockwise scenario with a ramp grade of 8%

Table 4. Counterclockwise scenario standardised performance parameters (grade: 8%)

Candidate	Scenario	Area [dka]	Standardised CO ₂ emissions	Standardised undiscounted profit
1	CW	179.5	0.8696	0.9931
2	CW	178.3	0.9004	0.9953
3	CW	180.9	0.8680	0.9901
4	CW	183.3	0.8378	0.9841
5	CW	185.2	0.7842	0.9777
6	CW	189.2	0.7096	0.9704
7	CW	188.9	0.7032	0.9693
8	CW	187.5	0.8048	0.9803
1	CCW	181.2	0.8740	0.9931
2	CCW	180.7	0.8982	0.9894
3	CCW	179.2	0.9244	0.9914
4	CCW	188.3	0.6753	0.9660
5	CCW	187.6	0.7003	0.9705
6	CCW	185.6	0.7949	0.9799
7	CCW	183.4	0.8071	0.9819
8	CCW	181.4	0.8461	0.9898

Therefore, it can be established that candidate 8 from the Clockwise scenario (Grade: 10%) has optimal performance parameters and therefore has to be chosen as the ultimate pit for this analysis. A close result is achieved by candidate 6 from the Counterclockwise scenario (Grade: 10%).

Fig. 17. Ultimate pit design solutions. Clockwise scenario (left) and counterclockwise scenario (right)

In both cases the exit point is from the side of the ex-pit crusher location and opposite to the waste dump location. In addition, the total amount of CO₂ truck emissions also seems to resemble a strong linear relationship with the total undiscounted profit. This can be explained by the fact that in open-pit mining a large percentage of the operational costs is attributed to haulage operations. This statement also applies in this case study, e.g., for the different scenarios of the open-pit mine, haulage costs vary between 50 and 70% depending on the ultimate pit design and volumes of ore and waste for different scenarios. Therefore, reducing transportation costs can contribute to the undiscounted profit of the mine, while at the same time the CO₂ emissions from truck operations can be reduced.

Figure 18 shows trend lines for both ramp grade scenarios, which prove that the undiscounted profit is strongly dependent on in-pit haul road length. Furthermore, the relationship remains rather consistent for all design alternatives, which leads to the conclusion that the undiscounted costs for the ultimate pit design are related strongly to in-pit haul distance. However, one should keep in mind that the trend line serves only as a general interpretation of the problem and not as a guideline for determination of the undiscounted costs via the in-pit road length. Although in rare cases, there could be a high value for R^2 , the estimated values are not consistent throughout all design alternatives. The reason for that deviation is that the ultimate pit design also affects the overall sum of the total costs.

Fig. 18. Correlations between in-pit haul length and standardised undiscounted profit

The Mean Average Error (MAE) of the in-pit Haul Road Length was estimated to be approximately 55 m for a 10% ramp grade and 49 m for an 8% ramp grade when solving the equations of their respective linear regression models. Therefore, the MAE is the threshold value which the difference between each two performance parameters of each two design alternatives must exceed for them to be ranked in a proper way.

If another approach is considered – to predict the undiscounted profit for each design via the haul distance length, the MAE value is 885 500 USD for a scenario with a 10% ramp grade and 676 205 USD for a scenario with an 8% ramp grade.

The distribution of the prediction error was estimated for the scenarios with 10% grade. A null-hypothesis of its normality was made with an $\alpha=0.05$ assumed. It proved out to be close to a normal one, by performing a Shapiro-Wilk test, which obtained a p-value of 0.786 (Figure 19).

Therefore, a confidence level can be assumed for further ranking future designed alternatives. Using the standard deviation of the error values, the following intervals can be defined:

- 95% level of confidence: $[-2\sigma, +2\sigma]$ (± 139.4 m);
- 99% level of confidence: $[-3\sigma, +3\sigma]$ (± 209 m).

Hence, depending on the level of confidence one wants to achieve regarding project alternatives, this is the value the differences of the optimised parameters of the design solutions or algorithm-based solutions should exceed. Furthermore, the profitability of the pit can be calculated in a similar manner.

Fig. 19. Normal Q-Q Plot of prediction error distribution of in-pit total ramp length

Conclusions

The current paper proposes a simple approach for haul road design optimisation, which can serve as a basis for the future implementation of algorithms in a tight search space. Rather than using a tree-based block model search approach, the use of 32 automatically designed ultimate pit candidates has not only provided a basis for determining the most feasible way of establishing a ramp design. It has also provided insight into the accuracy and limitations of other optimisation techniques achieving the same or a similar result. Last but not least, a threshold value was established based on the Mean Average Error (MAE), which provides a basis for ranking design alternatives or post-calculation algorithm-based solutions. Furthermore, for greater confidence certain intervals can be defined which provide a certain level of confidence for the future work of designers and programmers when indirectly using a certain parameter for the prediction of another one for more complex profit calculations. In addition, in order to obtain a more robust way of ranking project alternatives, one should know that pushback scenarios have to be included in future research on this topic, so that the change of haulage distances during the LOM is accounted for.

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